

ASYMPTOTIC HOMOGENIZATION FOR EFFECTIVE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF ELECTRIC COMPOSITE CONDUCTORS

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ABSTRACT:

An asymptotic theory based homogenization model has been developed to predict the effective mechanical properties of electric conductor consisting of conductor core and multi-layered composite insulations. The formulation of model and associated numerical algorithm can be applied to a complex geometry and material composition. The formulated homogeneous theory and model is implemented by finite element method. Computer code was developed and linked to commercial CAD and FEA package for engineering design application. Predictions and parametric studies are performed using an electric composite conductor. Results are compared to our previous analytical study to show the applicability of the model.

KEYWORDS: Homogenization theory, Electromagnetic composite conductor, Composite unit cell, Characterization

INTRODUCTION

Electrical machinery (EM) is an important component for military applications, which is used in electric drive platforms to electric launch systems. Compact, durable and highly mobile power generators and motors are the necessity to the success of all electrical systems. One of the integral elements in the system is the electromagnetic composite conductor. A structural layout of a typical electromagnetic composite conductor is shown in Figure 1. This composite conductor consists of an interior metallic conducting core with cooling channel, and exterior insulation layers made by different insulation materials and plain-woven fiber reinforced composite. Since the composite conductor is a base unit of the electrical winding that is a core component of the EM system, understanding the conductor mechanical properties is very important because these properties are the fundamental parameters used in the design and analysis of EM system under combined mechanical, electromagnetic, and thermal loading, as well as the system structural integrity, insulation, and service life [1, 2]. Because of the complex conductor structural winding and the material heterogeneity, an accurate prediction of the conductor effective mechanical properties is extremely difficult.

An attempt of using homogenization model and finite element approach to determine the effective mechanical properties of EM composite conductor was presented in references [3-5]. In

the reported model development, the homogenization was conducted based on a two-level hierarchy scheme. The level 1 homogenization scheme determines the effective mechanical properties of the metallic conducting core with cooling channel through the composite cylinder assembly model [6], and determines the effective mechanical properties of the out-wrapped layers through simple micro-mechanics model. The level 2 homogenization scheme predicts the effective mechanical properties of the EM composite conductor by using a combined sequences of the homogenization based on either the displacement prescribed or the traction prescribed boundary conditions applied to the representative volume element (RVE). Although a good agreement between the model and the finite element prediction, both the homogenization model and the finite element model have inherent limitations, for example, the upper and lower bound difference in the calculation of the RVE apparent modules associated with the specified type of boundary conditions [7], and the RVE boundary effect and size on the finite element prediction [8].

Asymptotic expansion based homogenization theory provides an alternative approach to predict the effective mechanical properties of multiphase composites with periodic or quasi-periodic microstructure [9, 10]. From a mathematical point of view, asymptotic expansion based homogenization theory adopts an asymptotic expansion and double scale techniques to establish stress and strain relations at both micro- and macro-scale levels, thus to predict the effective mechanical properties of the composites without accounting for any specific physical measurements. The expansion and implementation of the theory makes it possible to predict both the overall and local properties of composites. Comparing to the analytical and numerical models presented in [3-5], the asymptotic expansion based homogenization theory does not inherent the bound error and the boundary effect as indicated before.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of a composite conductor representative unit cell

This paper presents an asymptotic homogenization theory based modeling approach to predict the effective mechanical properties of composite conductor consisting of interior metallic conducting core with cooling channel, and exterior insulation layers made by different insulation materials and plain-woven fiber reinforced composite. A general description of the asymptotic homogenization theory and the modeling development for characterizing the EM composite conductor in the design point of view is presented. The effective properties of a representative unit cell of the composite conductor shown in Figure 1 are analyzed. A parametric study is conducted and compared with available analytical and numerical results. The calculated properties can then be used for a global analysis of an EM system with a complex winding

geometry and the heterogeneity. Since the EM system is usually analyzed with numerical techniques such as finite element method, the calculated effective mechanical properties and the local-global-local analytical technique enables the analysis at a detail level of individual constituents including geometries and properties for failure analysis.

ASYMPTOTIC HOMOGENIZATION FORMULATION

Consider a linearly elastic body, B with boundary ∂B , which consists of heterogeneous material regions. Let D and d be the macro and micro-length-scales of the body. The length scale of B is order of magnitude greater than that of the macro-length scale, D . Accordingly, a relative length-scale parameter is defined as

$$\varepsilon = \frac{d}{D} \ll 1. \quad (1)$$

The elasticity tensor field is defined as $C^\varepsilon(X)$ across the body B . Here X denotes a continuum point in B . Assuming B is subject to a surface displacement field, $u = u^0$ on ∂B , and the resulting displacement, strain, and stress fields in the body are expressed by $u^\varepsilon = u^\varepsilon(X)$, $\varepsilon^\varepsilon = \varepsilon^\varepsilon(X)$, and $\sigma^\varepsilon = \sigma^\varepsilon(X)$. The displacement specified equilibrium equation can be expressed by:

$$\nabla \bullet (C^\varepsilon(X) : (\nabla \otimes u^\varepsilon(X))) = 0 \quad \text{in } B. \quad (2)$$

In terms of a micro-length scale change in C^ε , replace the elasticity tensor field by

$$C^\varepsilon(X) \sim C(x) \quad (3)$$

Where

$$x = \frac{1}{\varepsilon} X \quad (4)$$

Consider the following singular-perturbation representation of u^ε :

$$u^\varepsilon(X) \sim \sum_{n=0} \varepsilon^n u^n(X, x). \quad (5)$$

Substituting (3) and (5) into (2), and replacing ∇ by $\nabla_X + \varepsilon^{-1} \nabla_x$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \varepsilon^{-2} \left\{ \nabla_X \bullet \left(C(x) : \left(\nabla_x \otimes u^0(X, x) \right) \right) \right\} \\ & + \varepsilon^{-1} \left\{ \nabla_X \bullet \left(C(x) : \left(\nabla_x \otimes u^0(X, x) \right) \right) + \nabla_x \bullet \left(C(x) : \left(\nabla_X \otimes u^0(X, x) + \nabla_x \otimes u^1(X, x) \right) \right) \right\} \\ & + \sum_{n=0} \varepsilon^n \left\{ \nabla_X \bullet \left(C(x) : \left(\nabla_X \otimes u^n(X, x) + \nabla_x \otimes u^{n+1}(X, x) \right) \right) \right. \\ & \left. + \nabla_x \bullet \left(C(x) : \left(\nabla_X \otimes u^{n+1}(X, x) + \nabla_x \otimes u^{n+2}(X, x) \right) \right) \right\} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

In order to solve (6), we assume

$$\nabla_x \otimes u^0(X, x) = 0 \quad (7)$$

If the "u⁰" is of a function of continuum variable X only, the terms of $O(\varepsilon^{-2})$ vanish in Equation (6). In addition, we assume that u^1 can be expressed in the following form:

$$u^1(X, x) = \chi^1(x) : (\nabla_X \otimes u^0(X)) \quad (8)$$

Accordingly, the terms of $O(\varepsilon^{-1})$ can be rewritten as follows

$$\left\{ \nabla_x (C(x) : (\nabla_x \otimes \chi^1(x) + I)) \right\} : (\nabla_X \otimes u^0(X)) = 0 \quad (9)$$

where I is a unit tensor. A physical interpretation of Equation (9) is that $\chi^1 : (\nabla_x \otimes u^0)$ represents a microscopic displacement field produced by the presence of the stress field, $C : (\nabla_X \otimes u^0) = C(x) : (\nabla_X \otimes u^0(X))$. Since the stress field does not satisfy equilibrium, oscillating micro-strains and associated stresses are generated. In other words, $\chi^1(x)$ encompasses the response of the microstructure with the macroscopic strain field, $(\nabla_X \otimes u^0 + (\nabla_X \otimes u^0)^T) / 2$. Therefore, if a suitable domain with suitable boundary conditions is introduced, χ^1 can be then determined. Once χ^1 is determined, the terms of $O(\varepsilon^0)$ are

$$\nabla_X \bullet \{C(x) : ((\nabla_x \otimes \chi^1(x) + I) : (\nabla_X \otimes u^0(X)))\} + \nabla_x \bullet \{C(x) : ((\nabla_X \otimes u^1(X, x) + \nabla_x \otimes u^2(X, x)))\} = 0 \quad (10)$$

The first term is the macroscopic equilibrium for $C : (\nabla_x \otimes \chi^1 + I) : (\nabla_X \otimes u^0)$ due to the stress of $O(\varepsilon^0)$. The second term is the microscopic equilibrium for $C : (\nabla_x \otimes u^1 + \nabla_x \otimes u^2)$ due to the stress of $O(\varepsilon^1)$. Introduce a constant tensor, effective mechanical properties \overline{C}^0 and the Equation of (10) is rewritten as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \nabla_x \bullet \{ \overline{C}^0 : (\nabla_x \otimes u^0(X)) \} + \{ \nabla_x \bullet \{ C(x) : (\nabla_x \otimes u^1(X, x)) + \nabla_x \otimes u^2(X, x) \} \} \\ & + \nabla_x \bullet \{ (C(x) : (\nabla_x \otimes \chi^1(x) + I - \overline{C}^0)) : (\nabla_x \otimes u^0(X)) \} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

It is shown that a periodically structural model of the sub-structure is used and \overline{C}^0 is given by

$$\overline{C}^0 = \frac{1}{V} \int_V C : (\nabla_x \otimes \chi^1 + I) dV \quad (12)$$

Once the effective mechanical properties, \overline{C}^0 are determined, the Equation (6) is solved up to $O(\varepsilon^0)$. The solution is given by u^0 , which satisfies

$$\nabla_x \bullet \{ \overline{C}^0 : (\nabla_x \otimes u^0(X)) \} = 0 \text{ in } B \quad (13)$$

With $u^\varepsilon \approx u^0$, the boundary conditions are expressed as follows

$$u^0(X) = u^0(X) \text{ on } \partial B \quad (14)$$

In order to calculate the effective mechanical properties \overline{C}^0 in Equation (12), χ^1 must be solved first in the homogenization equation (9) within the unit cell domain. For any complex geometry and material content of the unit cell, the homogenization equations have to be solved

by numerical techniques such as the finite element, boundary element or spectral method. FEM has been chosen to solve homogenization equation in this study. For an elastic case, the equation of asymptotic homogenization has very similar form as those in the typical elasticity problem. With the discretization of the domain of the unit cell and using shape function, the homogenization equation can be finalized as well-know form

$$Ku^i = f^i \quad i=1,2, \dots, 6, \quad (15)$$

where K is the global stiffness matrix and u^i (six cases for a three-dimensional problem) are components of χ^1 and f^i are “force” vectors.

SOLUTION ALGORITHM

A process to calculate the effective mechanical properties of EM composite conductor over a representative unit cell has been developed based on the developed asymptotic homogenization theory. The outline of the process is described in Figure 2. The process starts with an electric composite conductor configuration designed for EM machine. A solid model of the unit cell can be built with available commercial solid modeling software such as Pro/Engineer™. Then the solid model of unit cell is retrieved with conventional commercial FEA package such as ANSYS™ for mesh generation, and imposed of boundary conditions and material properties.

Figure 2 Outline of the process

We developed a computer program, called 3DHOMOG, based on the asymptotic homogenization theory in order to predict the effective mechanical properties of the unit cell. The 3DHOMOG is three-dimensional in nature and can also be applied to analyze composite constituents with anisotropic property. By the authors’ understanding, the incorporation of anisotropic material properties into the asymptotic homogenization theory to predict effective properties has not been reported elsewhere. The functional flowchart of the 3DHOMOG is explained in Figure 2. As shown in the figure, the 3DHOMOG starts with the information of node, element, material and boundary conditions obtained from the FEM model, computes local stiffness matrices, and then resembles into global stiffness matrix used for the effective properties calculation. The global stiffness matrix only needs to be assembled once for all the case studies (6 cases in total for a three dimensional model). The local and global force vectors are calculated and assembled for each case. After the boundary conditions are imposed and the global stiffness matrix is input into Equation (15), the micro-level displacements for various

cases can be calculated using Gaussian elimination method. Then the overall mechanical properties can be further calculated and output for evaluation.

Figure 3 Functional flowchart of 3DHOMOG

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PART 1: COMPARISONS WITH THE AVAILABLE RESULTS

We consider a composite conductor consisting of a metallic conductor core with cooling channel, and the exterior insulation layers made by various insulation materials and $\pm 45^\circ$ plain-woven glass-fiber reinforced composites. The fiber-reinforced composite provides mechanical and thermal properties, as well as an extra insulating protection. The metallic conductor core wrapped with the insulator composites is packed into an electric winding assembly. A schematic representation of the constituent materials and geometries for such a composite conductor unit cell and its model are presented in Figure 1.

The assumed constituent material properties and geometries are listed in Table 1. It shows a metallic core, two layers of insulation material, and anisotropic glass/epoxy composite because of the plain-woven fiber orientation. The constitute relation of the phase 3 glass/epoxy composite can be found in reference [3]. To verify the results using present process, it has been compared with the available results reported in references [3-5]. These comparisons are presented in Figure 4 for EM composite conductor without a cooling channel, and Figure 5 for EM composite conductor with a cooling channel, respectively.

Table 1 Assumed constituent material properties and geometries

Constituent material	Dimension	Material properties
Metallic conducting core	Width x height x depth (L x aL x L)	Young's modulus E_M : 69 MPa Poisson's ratio ν_M : 0.32 Diameter of cooling channel: D
Phase 1 insulation material	Thickness bL	Young's modulus E_{P1} : 3.45 MPa Poisson's ratio ν_{P1} : 0.35
Phase 2 insulation material	Thickness cL	Young's modulus E_{P2} : 0.52 MPa Poisson's ratio ν_{P2} : 0.35
Phase 3 Glass/Epoxy composite	Thickness dL $\pm 45^\circ$ plain woven	E-glass fiber: E_f : 72.45 MPa; ν_f : 0.22 Epoxy: E_m : 3.45 MPa; ν_m : 0.35 Fiber volume fraction V_f : 0.5

(a) effective young's modulus and shear modulus

(b) effective Poisson's ratio

Figure 4 Comparisons of effective mechanical properties for EM composite conductor without cooling channel (L=1", a=1.5, b=c=d=0.04, D=0")

(a) effective young's modulus and shear modulus

(b) effective Poisson's ratio

Figure 5 Comparisons of effective mechanical properties for EM composite conductor with cooling channel (L=1", a=1.5, b=c=d=0.02, D=0.3")

It can be seen from both figures that the asymptotic homogenization theory is applicable to predict the effective properties and the unit cell structural anisotropy of the EM composite

conductor. The prediction of effective mechanical properties of the EM composite conductor are agreed well with the results reported in reference [3] except three effective Poisson's ratios.

PART 2: PARAMETRIC STUDY

The variation of the conductor geometry, such as the change of the cooling channel diameter, change of the conductor core cross section and change of the insulation layer thickness on the effective properties of the conductor are studied and the results are presented in Figure 6, Figure 7 and Figure 8, respectively. It can be observed from Figure 6 that the increase of the cooling channel diameter will be in general decrease the effective modulus while increase the Poisson's ratio. Except E_{ZZ} in this case, all effective mechanical properties are not sensitive to the increase of the cooling channel diameter. This can be explained that increase of the cooling channel diameter will decrease the volume of the solid metallic core, which will generally decrease the strength of the material.

Figure 6: Effect of cooling channel diameter on the conductor effective properties
(Conducting core with cross-section: 1" x 1.5", insulation layer thickness: 0.02")

From Figure 7, it can be seen that the increase of the core cross section area by increase of the length of the core along Y direction will increase Young's moduli and E_{ZZ} while other moduli such as shear moduli and E_{XX} are not sensitive to the change. Poisson ratio ν_{XY} and ν_{XZ} will decrease while ν_{YZ} will increase when the length of the core along Y direction increase. From Figure 8 it can be seen that the increase of the insulation layer thickness will in general decrease the effective modulus of the conductor except of the Poisson's ratio ν_{XY} because of the decrease of the conducting core volume. The Young's modulus, E_{ZZ} , particularly sensitive to this change, while the shear modulus, and other Young's moduli and Poisson's ratio are less sensitive, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 7: Effect of conducting core cross section on effective properties (Conductor core cross-section: L x aL with L = 1", insulation layer thickness = 0.02", D = 0")

Figure 8: Effect of insulation layer thickness on conductor effective properties (Conductor core cross-section: 1" x 1.25", D = 0")

CONCLUSION

An asymptotic homogenization theory based modeling approach to predict the effective mechanical properties of composite conductor consisting of interior metallic conducting core with and without cooling channel wrapped with exterior layers made by different insulation materials and plain-woven fiber reinforced composite was presented. The modeling process and the computer algorithm for conducting homogenization analysis were described. The model predictions were compared to the available results presented in references [3-5]. Parametric studies for the effect of conductor geometry, such as the change of the cooling channel diameter, change of the conductor core cross section and change of the insulation layer thickness on the effective properties of the conductor were conducted and results were presented. The predictions of the effective modulus were compared well with the available analytical and numerical results as shown in the figures, which proves the applicability of the model to the EM conduct design. However, the predictions of the effective Poisson's ratios were generally low compared to the available analytical and numerical results. There is no available experimental data so far to verify

the applicability of the presented homogenization model and the analytical and numerical model reported in references [3-5], therefore, further investigation is needed to resolve this issue.

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